

Determination of *meta*-, *para*- and *ortho*-Nitroanilines using Spectrophotometric and Thermal Gradient Chromatographic Methods

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Manuscript received 1 August 1997, accepted 8 August 1997

A new sensitive spectrophotometric method based on diazotization and coupling reaction has been developed to determine the *meta*-, *para*- and *ortho*-nitroanilines. The nitroanilines were diazotized and coupled with phloroglucinol to give yellow azo-dyes, having λ_{\max} at 405, 435 and 450 nm respectively. The color systems obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.04–0.4 ppm for *m*-nitroaniline, 0.08–0.8 ppm for *p*-nitroaniline and 0.12–1.08 ppm for *o*-nitroaniline. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity have been determined. Thermal gradient chromatography has also been used for the simultaneous determination of *meta*-, *para*- and *ortho*-nitroanilines in a mixture. The methods have applied to the determination of nitroanilines in environmental samples.

In view of the significance of aromatic amino compounds in industry and environment, a large number of analytical methods have been reported¹⁻³. Here, a new sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method is reported for the determination of MNA, PNA and ONA based on a diazotization and coupling reactions. Nitroanilines are diazotized and coupled with phloroglucinol to give azo-dyes. The reaction conditions have been optimized and applied for their identification in a mixture using thermal gradient chromatography¹.

Results and Discussion

Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 0.04–0.4, 0.08–0.8 and 0.12–1.08 ppm of *meta*-, *para*- and *ortho*-nitroanilines respectively (i.e. 1–10, 2–20 and 3–27 μg per 25 ml of the final solution). The colored systems showed the maximum absorbance at 405, 435 and 450 nm for MNA, PNA and ONA respectively. The molar absorptivity were 2.76×10^5 , 1.53×10^5 , $1.01 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity 0.0006, 0.0009 and 0.001 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for MNA, PNA and ONA respectively. The effect of reagent concentrations was studied on all the three color systems. Sodium nitrite (1–2 ml) and phloroglucinol (1–2 ml) were found optimum for complete reaction.

The effects of time, temperature and pH on the color systems were studied. A time of 2 min was sufficient for full color development. The full color was developed above pH 11. Temperature in the range 20–60° had no appreciate deviation in the absorbance values. The azo-dyes were found stable over 72 h under optimum conditions.

The effect of the various species on the determination of the nitroanilines was studied. Most of the metal ions, organic and inorganic compounds did not interfere. Tolerance limits (ppm) of different ions and compounds in the determination of the nitroanilines (causing an error of $\pm 2\%$) were found as follows : Mn^{II} , Mg^{II} , Cu^{II} , nitrite and iodide

(400); Fe^{III} , Ca^{II} , phosphate and sulfate (300); pyridine (100); phenol and methanol (80); benzene and formaldehyde (20); 1-amino-2-naphthol (10).

Reproducibility of the method has been assessed by analyzing 10 μg of *m*-nitroaniline, 12 μg of *p*-nitroaniline and *o*-nitroaniline each per 25 ml over a period of 7 days. The standard deviation was ± 0.009 for each nitroaniline. The relative standard deviation values were 1.2, 2.4 and 3.3% for MNA, PNA and ONA respectively.

Analysis by thermal gradient chromatography : Migration of thermal waves, colored derivative of different nitroanilines were moved uniformly as concentric rings alongwith thermal waves but to different extent. The T_m values of colored derivatives were used for detection and identification of nitroanilines present in a sample. The T_m values were found 0.54, 0.44 and 0.49 for MNA, PNA and ONA respectively.

Application : The proposed method was successfully applied to polluted water samples. Synthetic samples were prepared by the addition of known amounts of nitroanilines to polluted water separately and then analyzed by the proposed method. The recovery was found to be about 98–99%.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF THE NITROANILINES ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) IN COKE OVEN EFFLUENT BY THE PROPOSED AND REPORTED METHODS*

Sample**	MNA	PNA	ONA
A	0.20 (0.19)	0.09 (0.09)	0.18 (0.18)
B	0.04 (0.04)	0.11 (0.10)	0.20 (0.19)
C	0.10 (0.09)	0.30 (0.29)	0.15 (0.14)
D	0.15 (0.13)	0.10 (0.10)	0.10 (0.10)

*Figures in parenthesis by reported method (Ref. 2).

**Amount of sample = 0.5 ml.

The proposed method was successfully applied to coke oven effluent. Aliquot (0.5 ml) of the effluent was analyzed as described above and the results are presented in Table 1.

The proposed methods are fast, simple and sufficiently sensitive for trace level analysis. The methods are suitable for industrial hygiene work.

Experimental

All spectral measurements were made with a Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer. A Systronics 331 pH-meter was used. Oven fitted with snapaction thermostat was used for providing required temperature.

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade or the best available quality. Double-distilled water was used throughout. Stock solutions (0.01 M) of nitroaniline in 2 M HCl and working standard containing 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of *meta*-, *para*- and *ortho*-anilines were prepared. A 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ was prepared from 0.1% aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (Merck). Solutions of 0.1 M phloroglucinol (Loba) and a 5 M NaOH (Merck) were prepared in water.

Spectrophotometric determination of the nitro-anilines : Aliquots containing standard solution of MNA (1–10 μg), PNA (2–20 μg) and ONA (3–27 μg) were diazotized by adding 2 M HCl and sodium nitrite (1–2 ml). The mixture was shaken gently for 2 min. Phloroglucinol (2 ml) was added in alkaline medium and then the mixture set aside for further 2 min. The solution was diluted to the mark with water and its absorbance was measured at 405, 435 and 450 nm for MNA, PNA and ONA respectively, against reagent blank.

*Thermal gradient chromatography determination of the nitroanilines*¹ : The method is based on differential migration of colored derivatives formed from the reaction of dia-

zotized nitroanilines with phloroglucinol under the influence of temperature gradient. On thin layer silica gel plate (the stationary phase) diazotized working standard solution was applied and kept it in an oven at 110° for 5 min. The plate was taken out and cooled. Intensity of color and radius of rings were measured. Under the influence of temperature, keeping force of gravitation and analytical conditions, uniform colored derivatives formed by a component in the mixture with a given reagent migrates according to molecular weight. When n number of components is likely to react with the given reagent it gave $(n+3)$ number of rings, one each for thermal wave, unreacted reagent and initial spot formed. Each colored derivative has a T_m value which is a characteristic of the compound. T_m values are similar to R_f values in planer chromatography.

$$T_m = \frac{\text{Radius of the ring due to component } (T_n)}{\text{Radius of the thermal value } (T_a)}$$

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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